

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Some Metal Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Base

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The interaction between bivalent metal ions, copper, nickel, cobalt and mercury with 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone have been studied in 70 volume per cent ethanol-water medium at different ionic strengths and at different temperatures, following the Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique, as applied by Van Uitert and Haas. It is observed that all the metals form 1 : 1 complexes with 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone as established by conductance measurements also. The ligand is biprotic. The refinement of results of stability constant were made by the method of Least-Square treatment after an algebraic transformation. The order of stability constants has been found to be $\text{Cu(II)} > \text{Ni(II)} > \text{Co(II)} > \text{Hg(II)}$. Thermodynamic parameters for all the metallic complexes have been calculated at different temperatures and ionic strengths.

RECENTLY interest has developed in cyanoderivatives which have found their usefulness in medicine as potent drugs¹. In several of such compounds, it has been observed that the bacteriostatic activity of the compound increases when it forms chelates with metal². No work on the reaction of metals with 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) is reported in the existing literature. The present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability of the Cu(II) , Ni(II) , Co(II) and Hg(II) complexes with 3-ASCAH derived by the condensation of 3-Aldehydosalicylic Acid and Cyanoacetic Acid Hydrazide.

Experimental

Synthesis of Ligand :

The 3-Aldehydosalicylic acid and Cyanoacetic acid hydrazide were prepared^{3,4} and taken in equimolecular proportions in alcoholic medium were made to condense after refluxing for two hours. 3-Aldehydosalicyledene cyanoacetyl hydrazone (3-ASCAH) separated as a crystalline compound. The deep yellow coloured needles of this Schiff base were purified by repeated crystallisation. The compound is soluble in alcohol and dioxane with sharp m.p. 208° .

Materials :

All reagents and chemicals used in the present work were of Analar B.D.H. grade. Pure distilled water, redistilled over alkaline permanganate and free from carbon dioxide, was used throughout the investigation. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared⁵. Perchloric acid of 0.1M and sodium perchlorate of 1 M were prepared by the

dilution with water. Metal ions of requisite concentrations were prepared in double distilled water and were estimated by EDTA⁶.

Apparatus :

The Elico-Conductivity Bridge Model CM-80 was used for the determination of composition of the complex with cell constant 1.09. The Metrohm pH meter Model E-350 A with wide range glass calomel electrode was used. Buffer solutions prepared from potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax were used for standardisation of the pH meter, which was done at the beginning of each titration and was checked after completion of it.

Conductometric Study :

Job's method⁷ was employed to establish the composition of the complexes conductometrically. The results show that the complexes contain metal ion and ligand in the ratio 1 : 1.

Potentiometric Study :

Bjerrum-Calvin^{8,9} technique modified by Irving-Rossotti¹⁰ was employed for which the following three mixtures were prepared : (A) Perchloric acid, (B) Perchloric acid+ligand solution and (C) Perchloric acid+ligand solution+metal salt solution. The concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different mixtures. An appropriate amount of the neutral sodium perchlorate (1 M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. These mixtures were titrated at different temperatures viz. 20° , 30° and $40^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ against standard carbonate free NaOH (0.1 M), potentiometrically. Since pH titrations were carried out in

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70 volume per cent ethanol-water medium, appropriate corrections in all pH meter readings were made on account of solvent as suggested by Van Uitert *et al*¹¹. A graph between pH and the volume of alkali added was plotted. The three titration curves were referred as (A) acid titration curve, (B) ligand titration curve and (C) complex titration curve.

Results

Proton-Ligand Stability Constants pK^H :

The values of $\bar{n}H$ at various pH values were calculated from the (A) acid and (B) ligand titration curves using the formula of Irving and Rossotti. Calculation of proton-ligand stability constants was carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}H$ against pH extended between 0 to 2 in the $\bar{n}H$ scale. The pK_1^H and pK_2^H values corresponding to $\bar{n}H=0.5$ and $\bar{n}H=1.5$ respectively were obtained from the curve. However, the best value of pK_1^H of the ligand was found from the plot of $\log \bar{n}H/(1-\bar{n}H)$ vs pH. This plot was found to be straight line with intercept equal to pK_1^H and slope equal to unity, suggesting that only one proton was dissociated. In the same way the value of pK_2^H was found from the plot of $\log (2-\bar{n}H)/(1-\bar{n}H)$ vs pH. The values of stepwise proton-ligand stability constants obtained at various temperatures are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT $\mu=0.1M$

Temperature	pK_1^H	pK_2^H	pK^H
20° ± 0.1°C	10.800	4.355	15.155
30° ± 0.1°C	10.575	3.850	14.425
40° ± 0.1°C	10.405	3.205	13.610

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants :

The stepwise stability constants of the metal complexes were determined by analysing the formula curves (\bar{n} versus pL). The values of \bar{n} , the average numbers of ligands attached per metal ion and the free ligand exponent pL were calculated from ligand and complex titration curves using the formula of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. From the titration curve it is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curves, which proves that the liberation of proton is due to chelation. \bar{n} values for each system were calculated upto the pH of precipitation. After this pH second buffer region start which explain the gradual consumption of hydrogen ion by metal in formation of metal hydroxide. The values of $\log k_1$ was obtained from the formation curves at $\bar{n}=0.5$. The plot of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} \right)$ against pL for the different metal systems was also drawn. From these graphical curves the values of $\log k_1$ were evaluated.

The better values could be computed using various computational methods¹². The constants are best evaluated by the "Least-Square Method", which makes use of all the experimental data and avoids subjective "smoothing" of data incidental to plot $\bar{n}/(\bar{n}-1)[L]$ against $(2-\bar{n})[L]/(\bar{n}-1)$ to obtain the intercept, $-K_1$ of the best straight line (1).

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)} \cdot K_1 K_2 - K_1 \quad \dots (1)$$

The values of stability constants at various temperatures and methods are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT $\mu=0.1$

Metal ion	$\log k_1$			Method*
	20° ± 0.1°C	30° ± 0.1°C	40° ± 0.1°C	
Copper	13.188	12.780	12.020	I
	13.295	12.886	11.987	II
	13.255	12.800	12.015	III
	13.199	12.897	11.985	IV
Nickel	11.950	11.420	10.740	I
	11.998	11.457	10.699	II
	11.962	11.437	10.737	III
	11.957	11.471	10.598	IV
Cobalt	9.512	8.955	8.965	I
	9.540	9.041	8.270	II
	9.550	8.862	8.312	III
	9.536	8.982	8.450	IV
Mercury	8.921	8.448	7.652	I
	8.941	8.463	7.602	II
	8.937	8.450	7.655	III
	8.901	8.467	7.598	IV

* I. Interpolation at half \bar{n} values, II. Interpolation at various \bar{n} values, III. Graphical method and IV. Least-square method.

The stability constants at zero ionic strength have also been determined from the plot of $\log k_1$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating it upto zero ionic strength Table 3.

TABLE 3—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS [Temp. 30 ± 0.1°C]

Metal ion	$\log k_1$			
	$\mu=0.00$	$\mu=0.02$	$\mu=0.05$	$\mu=0.1$
Copper	14.375	13.695	13.005	12.855
Nickel	13.075	12.455	11.705	11.500
Cobalt	10.450	9.815	8.975	8.885
Mercury	9.900	9.205	8.590	8.465

Thermodynamic Parameters :

The values of the overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for complexes have been calculated using Gibb's Helmholtz equation¹³, at different temperatures and different ionic strengths. Data for three temperatures and 0.01 ionic strength are tabulated in Table 4.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT $\mu=0.1$

Metal ions	Temp. in $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$	$-\Delta G$ (K.cal/mole)	ΔH (K.cal/mole)	ΔS (e.u.)
Copper	20	17.825	-13.8636	13.5201
	30	17.720		12.7273
	40	17.216		10.7105
Nickel	20	16.022	-16.9444	-3.1481
	30	15.834		-3.6646
	40	15.382		-4.9916
Cobalt	20	12.753	-19.4680	-22.9180
	30	12.416		-23.2739
	40	11.838		-24.3769
Mercury	20	11.961	-21.7857	-33.5313
	30	11.713		-33.2432
	40	10.960		-34.5869

Discussion

The result reveals that Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Hg(II) form 1 : 1 complex and the sequence of stability is found in the order : Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Hg(II) which is in accordance to Irving-Williams¹⁴. It may be mentioned here that inspite of the tendency of metal ions to hydrolyse in aqueous solution such effects have been ignored in this work as the metal chelates are stable in pH range studied.

The values of the stability constants reported in Table 2 are the concentration stability constants. Although the values obtained by the Least-square method would be more acceptable, it may be seen that the half integral values also are quite representative values of the stability constants. The values of $\log k_1$ are positive in all cases and increase on decreasing the temperature, which shows that lower temperature is favourable for the formation of complexes and for their stabilities. The free energied ($-\Delta G$) of formation of these chelates have lower values at 40° than 20° which indicates the decrease in reaction rate with increase in temperature. It is

further seen that values of enthalpy change are positive in all the cases indicating the energy absorption during chelate function. The results in Table 4 show that in all systems, entropy change accompanying the formation of complexes, are positive. As a result of this the entropy term strongly favours the complex formation and accordingly chelation effect is essentially an entropy. The very large entropy change is also justified by considering the greater availability of coordination sites on these metal ions.

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